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Abstract	This deliverable aims to identify the key ethical and legal requirements of the BLUE4ALL project in relation to the involvement of research contributors (i.e. stakeholders) for workshops, surveys and interviews, and particularly the identification and recruitment thereof. It also identifies the main Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues to consider in BLUE4ALL to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. These are identified as copyright and database protection, including confidential information, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs.
Keywords	Ethics, Intellectual Property Rights, Open Science, Legal Requirements

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Acronyms

Creative Commons (CC)

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Deliverable (D)

Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA)

Ethics Board (EB)

European Commission (EC)

Exploitation Plan (EP)

European Union (EU)

findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR)

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Horizon Europe (HEU)

Lead Partner (LP)

Marine protected area (MPA)

Open Science (OS)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Work Package (WP)

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable looks at the ethical and legal requirements of the BLUE4ALL project in relation to

1. Research contributors (i.e. stakeholders) for workshops, surveys and interviews, and particularly the identification and recruitment thereof. The practices and criteria used to identify, and recruit research participants are clearly formulated. Specifically, more detailed practical implementation methods and frameworks will be further elaborated upon within D4.1 Information sites engagement plan and D6.1- Dissemination and communication plan. In addition to that, research participants will be provided with informed consent procedures, including an informed consent template for research participation in the Stakeholder Engagement Groups established for each of the 13 Living Labs (D4.3).

Matters of data processing are also handled in relation to data management of research participants with further information on GDPR compliance, available within D7.3 (Data Management Plan).

2. The main Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues to consider in BLUE4ALL to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. These are identified as copyright and database protection, including confidential information, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs. Further information on processes ensuring IPR compliance and adherence to Open Science principles will be available in D7.3.

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2. Introduction

This report clarifies the roles and procedures for addressing the ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the project BLUE4ALL to ensure consistent application of legal and ethical frameworks and assist the full partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects and IPR protection. The strategy will be updated in M12 and M24.

Utilizing the ethical self-assessment in accordance with European Horizon Europe guidelines, one ethical issue is identified for the BLUE4ALL project: humans used in research for non-medical studies. Besides this issue, the processing of personal data is considered in this Ethics deliverable. The key data to be collected from stakeholders studied in BLUE4ALL will be reviewed by the dedicated Ethics Board.

This document also addresses BLUE4ALL's general approach to managing IPR. BLUE4ALL will follow the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and apply the FAIR principles to all project outputs. As stated in the DG Research & Innovation's study on Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), the OS paradigm poses new challenges to IPR. Here, we address the issue in a general manner, while the deliverables D7.3 Data Management Plan and D6.1 Dissemination and communication plan, will address the concrete IPR issues to be considered when applying the OS agenda in relation data management and exploitation and dissemination of results.

3. Ethical principles under Horizon Europe

Ethics is an integral part of research projects, which is also underlined by the European Commission (EC), specifically under Horizon Europe (HEU) research projects. The core of the ethical dilemma in research projects is to find a balance between two (or more) contradicting values. Though there are a number of absolute rules and regulations, the big challenge of ethics is one of judgement. The BLUE4ALL project will follow ethical compliance to respect the legal framework but also to enhance the quality of the research. We will follow existing EU, international and national guidelines. The HEU ethical requirements are anchored in the regulation HE Framework Programme Regulation 2021/695: Eligible actions and ethical principles (Article 18) and Ethics (Article 19). In Article 19 (1) of the regulation it is stated that:

"Actions carried out under the Programme shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international law, including the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols."

We follow therefore the ethical principles that are stated in this article and how they are applicable in the context of humans used in research, namely the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to protection of personal data, the right to physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination, the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

Personal data might be collected when engaging with stakeholders through interviews, surveys, workshops, or online applications.

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4. Intellectual Property Rights under Horizon Europe

IPR under Horizon Europe are set out in the Grant Agreement art. 16 and Annex 5 (Specific Rules). They should be further elaborated in the Consortium Agreement, e.g. as based on the DESCAs template. These agreements define the ownership of and access rights to results, as well as the rules governing joint ownership, exploitation and dissemination of results, confidentiality, access rights to existing background, and Open Science.

Based on the DG Research and Innovation's report study on Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), considerations should always be made regarding how to balance OS and IPR:

- The concrete application of IPR and OS principles in relation to exploitation and dissemination of results, i.e. this should be included in the dissemination, and exploitation plan.
- The concrete application of IPR in relation to the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data) i.e. this should be included in the data management plan and there should be a defined process for checking the validity of the consent of the rights holder or whether an exception/limitation applies.

5. Role of the Ethics Board in BLUE4ALL

The project has established the Ethics Board (EB) involving all WP leads and some of the Advisory Board participants to warrant compliance with fundamental ethical principles present in the Nuremberg Code, European Textbook on Ethics in Research, and EC Ethics Appraisal Procedure. The EB will ensure consistent application of the legal and ethical frameworks references in this document, and assist the full partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects incl. the 'do no significant harm' principle and IPR protection. The EB will specifically review documents, tasks and deliverables mentioned in this strategy. Generally, the EB will be involved by the LP (RBINS) as soon as any ethical or IPR related question arises beyond the issues already identified.

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6. Implementing HEU ethical principles in BLUE4ALL

During the BLUE4ALL project, surveys, workshops and interviews with several stakeholders will be conducted. Participation thereof will be entirely voluntary. An informed consent procedure will be used to inform participants of the voluntary nature of their involvement, project aims, use of data, and data protection regulation and implications of the research participation. This chapter describes the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants with reference to the relevant HEU ethical principles, the informed consent procedure and the data and sampling collection of research participants.

6.1 Ethical principles in context

Ethical principles under Horizon Europe can be applied to the context of research participation:

- The principle of proportionality, meaning that cause and effect or action and consequences should be proportional. Questions posed during interviews and surveys should be proportional to the project aims;
- The right to privacy, meaning the absence of public attention. Information collected during interviews and surveys will be treated confidentially.
- The right to protection of personal data. Resulting data from interviews, surveys and workshops will be protected and stored securely in compliance with latest GDPR 2016/697 regulations, which will further specified in D 7.3 (DMP)
- The right to physical and mental integrity of a person. No physical or mental pressure will be applied in any form during the recruitment procedure and the informed consent procedure
- The right to non-discrimination. No discrimination during the identification and recruitment of research participants will take place. Meaning, no discrimination based on colour, race, gender, religion, political preference, age, nationality or marital status. The BLUE4ALL consortium has an international character with partners with a headquarters in over 13 different countries and people from many nationalities are represented within the consortium
- The need to ensure high levels of human health protection. We ensure that research participants will only participate in interviews, surveys and workshops under high levels of human health protection.

The above principals will be adhered to throughout the BLUE4ALL project and applied in the communication and dissemination activities, recruitment and building of Information sites, Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living Labs, as well as the identification, recruitment, data gathering, and processing of survey and workshop participants. They will in particularly be addressed in the specific contexts of WP 4: Deliverable 4.1, Deliverable 4.3, WP 5: Deliverable 5.1 and WP6: Task 6.3, Task 6.4.

Furthermore, guidelines on safety and protection in relation to the activities to be carried out in the context of the project (not related to testing or administration of human based research, as this is not applicable in this context) will be adhered to, providing robust ethical standards to those working within the project.

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6.2 Identification and recruitment of research participants

The identification and recruitment of research participants for interviews, surveys and workshops is further elaborated upon within the efforts of WP 4: Deliverable 4.1 (Information sites engagement plan), and Deliverable 4.2 (Living Lab testing package) and Deliverable 4.3 (Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living labs).

In general, participants are recruited from existing networks and approached during conferences and workshops. Such networks include the existing scientific, professional, and industrial connections, working groups, and initiatives for which BLUE4ALL partners and the consortia as a whole is involved with. Requests for research participants may also be communicated through the project website and the project newsletter to engage with and utilize the community interested in the developments of the project. Furthermore, additional recruitment procedure may be developed in order to fulfil gaps existing in the already accessible pool of candidates, these can include directed queries to governance and research networks cited as of high relevance, advice on networks and participants from the Information sites and Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living Labs from task deliverables 4.1 and 4.3 respectively.

When identifying and recruiting research participants (i.e. stakeholders), all partners of the BLUE4ALL project will comply with the ethical principles. Stakeholders will be identified and grouped in a stakeholder register that is internal to the BLUE4ALL project. The register allows to visualize e.g. relative power and interest of stakeholders on a relative scale, however, this will not be done on a specific user by user basis but rather the power structure of generalized groupings of potential and identified stakeholder groups, thereby not utilizing personalized data from any of the research participants and nullifying any concerns towards personal information protection as this will not be applicable.

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6.3 Data collection and data protection

This paragraph describes the GDPR directive, its principles and how the BLUE4ALL project adopts protection measures to assure fair adequate and informed research participation.

For data collection during interviews, surveys and workshops, we comply to the latest GDPR regulation (GDPR 2016/697). In Article 4(1) it is stated that personal data means

“any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”

In Article 4(2) it is stated that processing means

“any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.”

According to the EC’s guidance on Ethics and data protection (2021), data protection should be included by design and default in the context of research and development by applying the following measures when relevant:

- Pseudonymisation and anonymisation of personal data;
- data minimisation;
- applied cryptography (e.g. encryption and hashing);
- using data-protection focused service providers and storage platforms; and
- arrangements that enable data subjects to exercise their fundamental rights (e.g. as regards direct access to their personal data and consent to its use or transfer).

6.3.1 Personal Data

Personal data collected for the purposes of the BLUE4ALL project, will only be stored, analysed and used anonymously. Personal data will not be made public and will have restrictions for usage (i.e., only within the project and for the purposes of the defined tasks).

This document focuses on the processes related to involvement of stakeholders in research. Further specification of the GDPR compliance in relation to all storage and processing of personal data is covered by Deliverables 7.4 Data Management Plan, which will be updated throughout the project.

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6.4 Data protection measures

The above considerations can be translated to data protection measures. These will be followed and applied where possible.

6.4.1 Data collection

Data resulted from surveys, workshops and interviews will be collected according to the minimization principle. This means we only collect data adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the project aims. Thus, the only information collected via interviews, meetings/workshops related to the information sites & stakeholder engagement groups in WP4. An informed consent statement should inform all research participants of the terms and conditions. Interactive webinars will also be sources of information collection serving general knowledge exchange between the MPA managers, planners, industry and researchers. Information may be collected in an audio-visual format (e.g. video of the webinar) and explicit agreement will be required from each participant for the recording and publishing of the material.

6.4.2 Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation

Any data will be anonymized, where possible, and else data will be pseudonymised. The Data Protection Working Party, which is an independent European advisory body on data protection and privacy, published a document on Anonymisation techniques (Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques, 2014). Here generalization, randomization techniques are discussed. Also, pseudonymisation, which is different from anonymisation is considered here. For anonymisation, the data must be stripped until the point where the data subject is no longer identifiable. Anonymisation techniques like aggregation will be applied if relevant. Here data is displayed only in total scores, omitting individual responses. For example, age 25 will be grouped in the category age 20-30. If anonymisation is not achievable, pseudonymisation techniques can be applied, so that the source of information cannot be traced back to the data. Direct identifiers (e.g. names) will be replaced with indirect identifiers (e.g. numbers). Data masking could be applied, where some personal identifiers are stripped out, while others remain.

6.4.3 Data Security, storage and encryption

Practical data security, storage and encryption measures provided by the European University Institute (EUI, 2019) that will be used where possible:

- User authentication: verify user by a password, considering length, a mix of letters and no ties to your personal information;
- Access control: a mechanism to allow or deny access to certain data;
- Storage security: storing data in a way that prevent unauthorised access, for example by: operating system controls, use of passwords to access electronic files, local encrypted storage, database encryption;
- Data retention will cover the duration of the project and not longer;
- Communication security: safe electronic communication for transferring data: encrypted communications (SSL/TLS, safe URLs starting with https://); firewall systems and access control lists; anti-virus and anti-malware systems; protect data when physically transferred.

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6.4.4 Data Transfer

Regarding the data collected for the purposes of the communication and dissemination activities of the project, they will not be transferred to third parties either in the original form or in copies. Data might be published in reports, scientific publications, and other forms of publication, however, in anonymized form only.

The EB, including legal experts at various partner institutes, will guarantee that this process, including the information for the individuals about data protection issues, fully complies with national and EU laws.

6.4.5 Informed consent procedure

Individuals participating in any form of stakeholder engagement activities that involve the collection of data, will be informed comprehensively about the intended use of the information collected from them and have to agree to the data collection for scientific purposes with their active approval in form of a written consent. In addition, individuals will be informed about data security, anonymity and use of data as well as asked for accordance. The Informed consent form template is attached in Annex A of this document.

6.5 Website data collection

The BLUE4ALL website should serve as a source of information on the project. The following personal data might be stored while using the website: name of internet domain, IP address of the accessing computer, pages visited and actions performed throughout the website.

The data may be processed in order to optimize the website by improving the quality of the available information, website ergonomics, website management, website navigation and to generate statistics from this information. The collected data will not be provided to any third party or processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind, particularly in the matter of data retention, as will also be specified in Deliverable 7.3 (DMP).

The website is anticipated to store cookies. These are small text files that are saved on the computer, which the browser can access. They increase the user-friendliness of the website. In case the website uses cookies, a pop-up will ask you for a permission first.

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7. Implementing IPR in BLUE4ALL

To ensure that all knowledge and intellectual property generated by BLUE4ALL is managed correctly and adequately protected, the BLUE4ALL Consortium Agreement addresses the ownership and management of both project results and pre-existing rights (i.e., background included), as well as access rights and confidential information. Results are owned by the partner that generates them, including the case of joint ownership and the principles governing this.

The main IPR issues to consider in BLUE4ALL are copyright and database protection in relation to datasets and publications, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs. As stated in the DG Research & Innovation's study on Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), the OS paradigm poses new challenges to IPR, but the two are in no way incompatible.

In BLUE4ALL, the knowledge co-elaboration and open science approach is reflected in several inclusive practices and co-creation methods applied (e.g. T. 4.2, T4.3 and WP5 the development of an online blueprint). The BLUE4ALL research will be made openly available unless otherwise explicitly specified, and under the conditions that no confidential information is involved and that appropriate identification of origin and conditions of reuse is applied (e.g. CC licenses).

The Blue4All project will follow the FAIR principles:

- *Findable*: The data and metadata can be found by the community after their publication, using search tools.
- *Accessible*: (Meta)data are accessible and can therefore be downloaded by other researchers using their identifiers.
- *Interoperable*: Both the data and the metadata should be described following the rules of the community, using open standards, in order to allow for their exchange and reuse.
- *Reusable*: (Meta)data can be reused by other researchers, since their origin and conditions of reuse are clear.

D 6.1 will further address the dissemination and communication strategy.

D 6.4 will further address the means of exploitation applied in the project

D 7.3 (DMP) will further address the protection of IPR in relation to the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data produced under BLUE4ALL.

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9. Annex A Document of Informed Consent

PROJECT TITLE BLUE4ALL

START DATA OF THE PROJECT 01-01-2023

END DATE OF THE PROJECT 31-12-2026

PROJECT WEBSITE www.BLUE4ALL.eu (under construction)

You have been invited to participate in research under the BLUE4ALL project in the form of a survey, workshop or an interview. Before participation, please read the information below carefully. If statements in the document are unclear to you, do not hesitate to ask the contact researcher for clarification.

1. Project summary

BLUE4ALL will align top-down regulatory demands about European (networks of) MPAs with bottom-up societal expectations as a guarantee for achieving effective, efficient and resilient MPAs and networks of MPAs which meet EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 objectives. By mobilizing stakeholders from BLUE4ALL’s 25 information sites and Living Labs, i.e. locations across the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North-East Atlantic regions where (networks of) MPAs have been established and from which lessons learned can be drawn about success and failure relative to how challenges were tackled, we will co-create robust and replicable social, governance, ecological and environmental tools to meet conservation and/or restoration objectives in socially sustainable and acceptable ways. These science-based tools will be tested in Living Labs, i.e. locations where (networks of) MPAs are in the process of establishment and where these tools can be fed into the ongoing MPA process. The operationalized and tested frameworks will ultimately be generalized into a Blueprint Platform for the co-creation of effective, efficient and resilient (networks of) MPAs. This scheme will separate generically encountered challenges and applied solutions from MPA (network) specific challenges and solutions and develop guidance in a user-friendly manner to end-users (i.e. MPA (network) managers and authorities). This guidance will take the shape of an interactive web-based Blueprint Platform directing the end-users to those challenges and solutions most applicable to their site(s). User-friendliness and applicability will be maximized by cross-checking the Blueprint Platform development with the actors and stakeholders of the Living Labs throughout the whole process of its development. Knowledge transfer and interaction with stakeholders and society-at-large at local to regional scales will lead to the development of a platform for MPA networking to interact with communities of practice boosting the BLUE4ALL legacy to its ultimate goal to restore our oceans and waters.

2. Purpose of data collection

You have been invited to participate in an interview, survey or workshop. Resulting data will be specifically used to

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3. Benefit of participation

Participation is on an entirely voluntary basis and you may not directly benefit. However, you will make a substantial contribution to the BLUE4ALL project aims.

4. Risks of participation

There are no risks foreseen in participation

5. Compliance with ethical and legal regulations

We comply with EU and national ethical and legal regulations, including the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation 2016/680) framework of the EU.

6. Privacy and data protection

Data resulted from surveys and interviews will be recorded and stored on secure servers. This data will not include any personal identification, so that data cannot be traced back to you as the source of the data. Data might be processed and analysed for publication in reports, scientific journals and other forms of project outputs, only in anonymized form. None of the data will be transferred to third parties. Retention time of the original research data is the same as the project duration, although the anonymized resultant data may be stored for longer periods of time to be used in future research.

7. Withdrawal of participation

At any point you may withdraw from participation by stopping the interview, survey or workshop.

8. Researcher contact

In case of any issues or questions you can contact:

Name: and contact:

9. Consent statement

By signing this form, I state that I have read all information on this document of informed consent, I understand the information provided, and I agree with the terms and conditions provided on the informed consent document.

.....

Research Participant

.....

Signature

.....

Date

.....

Researcher

.....

Signature

.....

Date